

Lyceum: a fully-local multimodal system for narrated visualisation of mathematical textbooks

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ABSTRACT

We describe *Lyceum*, a fully-local multimodal system that ingests a static mathematics or statistics PDF textbook and turns it into an interactive, narrated whiteboard. An offline pass builds a per-book math semantic graph that captures every formula, variable, concept and dependency before any narration starts. At run time, an orchestrator queries this graph per spoken clause and emits a small vocabulary of typed visual primitives — passage cards, book figures, curated canonical diagrams, formula cards, reference cards and cross-section connectors — timed against the audio clock so the spoken track and the whiteboard cannot drift apart. A three-tier quality-assurance suite audits every ingested book and a self-healing loop repairs OCR-degraded formulas against the source PDF. No external API is reachable from any process. We evaluate the system on *The Elements of Statistical Learning* (Hastie et al., 2009) and report routing, retrieval, visual-emission, math-graph coverage, inline-math-detector and narration-quality numbers in Section 27.

1. Introduction

A static PDF textbook embeds three mostly disjoint signals — prose, typeset mathematics, and pre-rendered figures — and provides no mechanism to (a) read the prose aloud, (b) re-synchronise an illustration to the moment a concept is mentioned, or (c) re-render a formula on demand. This work targets that gap end-to-end while satisfying a strict locality constraint: every model invocation runs on the user’s own hardware.

Scope. We address a narrowly-defined problem: given a mathematics/statistics PDF and a topic or free-form question, produce a synchronised audio stream and a visual stream of cards on a whiteboard, where the visual stream is grounded in the source corpus when possible and synthesised under explicit quality and latency budgets when not.

Contributions.

1. A typed per-clause emission pipeline (Section 15): eight visual primitives (one chapter-zoom-only), six dedup sets, all timing pegged to the audio clock.
2. An **offline math semantic graph** (Section 19): 4 node types (VAR, FORMULA, PASSAGE, CONCEPT) and 11 edge types built once per book (ESLII: 1,723 formulas, 22,335 edges in ≈ 100 s), then queried by the runtime for sub-expression folding, citation arrows and cross-section ghost cards.

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3. A three-tier visualisation stack (Section 16): book figures with on-demand PDF cropping; a 12-entry curated SVG library selected by embedding similarity with a margin guard; a local-LLM fall-back under a 1.6 s budget.
4. A **three-tier quality-assurance suite** plus a **math-fidelity agent** (Section 17): an offline data-quality inspector (18 A-checks), a runtime smoke harness, and an agentic loop that crops the source-PDF region around each cite marker and iterates VLM-vs-text-LLM until parsed and rendered LaTeX match. Self-Refine (Madaan et al., 2023) and Reflexion (Shinn et al., 2023) are the closest prior agentic patterns; ours is specialised to math-formula OCR repair.
5. An **audio-clock synchronisation engine** (Section 20): a single `requestAnimationFrame` loop polling `AudioContext.currentTime` replaces every `setTimeout` schedule. Drift is impossible by construction; pause/resume falls out of `ctx.suspend()` for free; sentence- and section-level narration navigation (Section 21) reuses the same timeline structure.
6. A topic-path planner (Section 12), a chapter-zoom mode (Section 13), a 10-intent utterance router (Section 9), pre-computed concept- and formula-layer sidecars (Section 10), a tangent panel (Section 11), local voice input (Radford et al., 2023) (Section 22) and resumable sessions (Section 23), all driven from the same orchestrator.
7. A **purely local** stack (Table 2) — a quantised text LLM, an embedding model, a vision-language model, and the Kokoro TTS, all served from the user’s own machine — and an **auto-pipeline** (Section 25) that runs every builder, both inspector tiers, and the fidelity agent the moment a new book is uploaded, with no human in the loop.

2. Related work

Lyceum sits at the intersection of intelligent tutoring, retrieval-augmented generation, mathematical knowledge representation, mathematical diagrammatic synthesis, and audio-visual presentation under multimedia learning principles. We review each in turn and end with a contribution matrix that situates Lyceum against the closest prior systems.

Intelligent tutoring systems (ITS). Cognitive Tutors (Anderson et al., 1995) grounded a generation of school-deployed mathematics tutors in production-rule student models; AUTOTUTOR (Graesser et al., 2005) introduced mixed-initiative dialogue with a virtual conversational agent; the canonical meta-analysis (VanLehn, 2011) reports that well-engineered ITS approach human one-on-one tutoring on learning outcomes. Recent LLM-backed tutors fold large-model question answering into the same loop, but typically retain the same affordances: free-form chat with optional figure rendering. Lyceum departs from this lineage in three respects. First, it is anchored to a fixed textbook corpus and inherits the corpus’s prose, figures, and cross-reference graph as the source of truth, rather than treating the LLM as the canonical content store. Second, the surface produced is not a dialogue transcript but a synchronised *audio + chalkboard* stream where every clause emits typed visual operations. Third, the entire stack runs on the learner’s hardware — no external API is queried at any stage.

Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG). Retrieval-augmented generation (Lewis et al., 2020) grounds generative models in a non-parametric memory; dense passage retrieval (Karpukhin et al., 2020) provides the embedding-based recall half of modern hybrid pipelines, and reciprocal rank fusion (Cormack et al., 2009) the canonical late-fusion combiner. A recent survey (Gao et al., 2023) catalogues post-retrieval techniques including reranking, self-reflection and constrained decoding. Lyceum uses a standard BM25 (Robertson and Zaragoza, 2009) + dense embedding (Zhang et al., 2025) hybrid with RRF, but adds two domain-specific constraints rarely seen together in the RAG

literature. (i) The generator’s output is forced through a sanitiser (Section 8) that strips LaTeX and Markdown so the same string is read aloud and captioned, and (ii) visual operations emitted alongside the spoken clause are not free-text but typed primitives drawn from a pre-built math semantic graph (Section 19), so the generator cannot drift visually even when it drifts textually.

Mathematical knowledge representation. OMDOC (Kohlhase, 2006) and Content MathML / OpenMath define interoperable formats for mathematical documents and content dictionaries; OntoMathPRO (Nevzorova et al., 2014) provides a linked-data hub of mathematical concepts. Tangent-CFT (Mansouri et al., 2019) learns embeddings over formula trees for retrieval. These efforts target cross-corpus interoperability and formula search. Lyceum’s math semantic graph is narrower: it is built once per book, uses a fixed schema of 4 node and 11 edge types, and is consumed at runtime by a single narrator process to anchor sub-expression containment, citation links, and cross-section ghost cards. Phase 2 of our roadmap (Section 29) maps the in-graph identifiers onto OntoMathPRO and Tangent-CFT for cross-book reuse; the present work reports the in-book backbone only.

Mathematical diagrammatic synthesis. Penrose (Ye et al., 2020) is the closest architectural analogue to Lyceum’s three-tier visualisation stack: it accepts a Domain (concepts), Substance (an instance) and Style (visual mapping) triple and produces publication-quality diagrams via constraint-based layout. Penrose targets static authoring; Lyceum targets a runtime narrator that emits diagrams under a per-clause latency budget while audio plays. In the parsing direction, AI2D (Kembhavi et al., 2016) and AI2D-RST (Hiippala et al., 2021) provide annotated diagram corpora for science-textbook understanding, and Inter-GPS (Lu et al., 2021) treats geometry diagrams as a formal-language target for symbolic solvers. Our 12 curated SVG generators (Tier-2) play a Penrose-style role for statistical-learning topics; the LLM fall-back (Tier-3) plays a generative role under structural and vision-language inspection (Section 17).

Multimedia learning and audio-visual contiguity. Mayer’s cognitive theory of multimedia learning (Mayer, 2009) predicts that simultaneous, spatially and temporally contiguous narration and imagery improve retention; Tversky (Tversky, 2011) catalogues the visual patterns that effective explanatory diagrams reuse. Lyceum’s audio-clock-locked `requestAnimationFrame` loop (Section 20) is an engineering instantiation of the temporal-contiguity principle: by polling `AudioContext.currentTime` as the single source of truth, the yellow word marker, the chalkboard add/erase events and the running transcript cannot drift relative to the spoken track — timing coherence is a property of the architecture rather than a tuning parameter.

Local-only large model serving. Quantisation methods such as AWQ (Lin et al., 2024) and inference runtimes such as vLLM (Kwon et al., 2023) have recently made it practical to host 14 B-parameter LLMs and 7 B-parameter vision-language models on a single workstation. Lyceum’s stack (Table 2) takes this hardware envelope as a hard design constraint. We are not aware of a prior intelligent-tutoring or narrated-RAG system that runs end-to-end without any external API call.

Self-healing agentic loops. Self-Refine (Madaan et al., 2023) and Reflexion (Shinn et al., 2023) establish the pattern of an LLM critiquing and refining its own output across iterations. Lyceum’s math-fidelity agent (Section 17) is a domain-specialised instance: the critic is a vision-language model that compares the parsed LaTeX rendering against a crop of the source PDF, the refiner is a text-LLM rewriting only when the critic disagrees, and the loop terminates with a typed verdict (`MATCH`REPAIRED`DEGRADED`UNVERIFIABLE`) that gates the math-graph patch.

Table 1

Lyceum versus closest prior systems. ✓ = supported, = partial, ĩ = absent or out of scope. “Sync” = audio-locked visual emission; “Local” = end-to-end on user hardware; “Graph” = persistent per-corpus formula/concept graph driving narration.

System	Corpus-grounded	Narration	Visuals	Sync	Local	Graph
Cognitive Tutor (Anderson et al., 1995)		ĩ		ĩ	✓	ĩ
AutoTutor (Graesser et al., 2005)		✓			ĩ	ĩ
RAG chatbot (Lewis et al., 2020)	✓	ĩ	ĩ	ĩ	ĩ	ĩ
Penrose (Ye et al., 2020)	ĩ	ĩ	✓	ĩ	✓	
Inter-GPS (Lu et al., 2021)	ĩ	ĩ		ĩ	✓	
Lyceum (this work)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 2

Local-only model stack. No external API is reachable from any process.

Service	Port	Model	Role
vLLM (Kwon et al., 2023)	8000	Qwen2.5-14B-Instruct-AWQ (Qwen Team, 2024)	Q&A synthesis; Tier-3 SVG
vLLM	8003	Qwen3-Embedding-0.6B (Zhang et al., 2025)	Dense retrieval; topic match
vLLM	8004	Qwen2.5-VL-7B-Instruct-AWQ (Bai et al., 2025)	Visual inspection; equation OCR
Kokoro (hexgrad, 2025)	—	Kokoro-82M (StyleTTS 2)	Speech synth (af_heart)
HTTP	8001	stdlib <code>http.server</code>	SSE, static, REST

Position. Table 1 contrasts Lyceum with the closest prior systems across the dimensions that matter for narrated, corpus-grounded mathematical exposition.

To our knowledge, Lyceum is the first system that ingests a static mathematics PDF, builds a per-book persistent semantic graph, narrates the text with audio-clock-locked visual emission, and runs entirely on the user’s hardware. Each individual ingredient has prior art; the contribution is the integration and the design choices that make it a working, reproducible artifact.

3. System overview

Figure 1 shows the components and data flow. The system has four long-lived processes (HTTP server, one text-LLM server, one embedding server, one vision-LLM server) and one short-lived subprocess (the TTS worker). The text-LLM server hosts a single quantised Qwen2.5-14B-Instruct-AWQ checkpoint via vLLM and is reused by three callers — Q&A synthesis, the low-similarity intro path, and Tier-3 SVG synthesis (Section 16).

4. Layers of abstraction

The system is layered. Reading top-down, Figure 2, each layer hides everything below it from the layer above:

1. **User surface** — a single web page with a topic box, an Ask box, voice input, a main whiteboard and a tangent (answer) panel. Section 21.

2. **Dialogue and intent** — the router classifies an utterance into one of ten intents and either applies a session-level control immediately or hands a typed plan-request to the planner. Section 9.
3. **Plan** — a deterministic `NarrationPlan` of clauses anchored at `home_nids`; the topic mode produces a single-rooted plan (Section 12); the read-book and chapter / section overviews use the depth-decay outline planner (Section 14).
4. **Per-clause emission** — the orchestrator turns each plan clause into a `StreamEvent` (text + WAV stamps + typed visual ops); audio chunks stream through the Kokoro subprocess. Section 15.
5. **Visual ops + dedup state** — seven typed primitives (Table 6) plus six per-session `seen_*` sets; visuals are looked up against the offline math semantic graph (Section 19) before any runtime detection runs.
6. **Frontend sync** — a single `requestAnimationFrame` loop polls `AudioContext.currentTime` and drives every visual update from a per-seq `ClauseTimeline`. Section 20.
7. **Local model fabric** — vLLM hosts the text LLM, the embedding model and the vision LLM; Kokoro is a TTS subprocess; no request ever leaves the user’s machine. Table 2.

The remainder of this paper walks the system at three matching scales: **(i) the request lifecycle** — what happens between a user clicking Topic and the first audio reaching the browser (Section 5); **(ii) the per-clause pipeline** — what the orchestrator does inside a single yield (Section 15); and **(iii) the math extraction layer** — what the offline build computes once per book so the runtime can look up rather than re-derive (Section 19).

5. Request lifecycle

A single Topic click triggers six observable events. Figure 3 traces them; the timing column is the median measured against the ESLII corpus on the test workstation.

6. Book IR

The corpus is a recursive `BOOKNODE` tree with three orthogonal overlays (Listing 1). PDF parsing uses PyMuPDF (Artifex Software, 2026) and is deterministic given a fixed PyMuPDF version.

Table 3

ESLII (Hastie et al., 2009) corpus statistics after ingestion (the “v2” figure pass is the post-hoc PyMuPDF re-extraction of §26; *equations sidecar* is the count of equations recovered by the local VLM-OCR step described in §26).

Quantity	Count
BOOKNODES (all kinds)	384
chapter	21
section	168
subsection	169
subsubsection	15
FIGUREREFS (original + v2)	129
CROSSREFS	2,554
CONCEPTENTRYS	30
Equations sidecar (VLM-OCR)	44
On-disk corpus JSON	26.6 MB

Listing 1: Book intermediate representation, abbreviated.

```
class BookNode:
    nid: str; kind: str; number: str|None; title: str
    page_start: int; page_end: int
    body_text: str
    children: list[BookNode]; meta: dict

class FigureRef:
    fid: str; home_nid: str; page: int
    caption: str; bbox: tuple[4 floats]
    image_path: str; meta: dict

class CrossRef: # citation edge
    from_nid: str; to_nid: str; label: str; char_offset: int

class ConceptEntry: # concept index
    cid: str; canonical: str; aliases: list[str]
    definitions: list[(home_nid, text)]
    templates: list[ConceptTemplate]
    figure_refs: list[str]; embedding: tuple
```

Table 3 reports the corpus we use throughout the paper.

7. Hybrid retrieval

Given a query q and a candidate set $C = \hat{n}_i$ of body-bearing BOOKNODES, we score each n_i with a fused rank.

Lexical (BM25). The lexical retriever follows the standard BM25 formulation (Robertson and Zaragoza, 2009)

$$\text{BM25}.q, n/ = \text{IDF}.t/ \frac{f.t, n/ \cdot k_1 + 1/}{f.t, n/ + k_1 (1 * b + b \frac{n/}{n})}, \quad (1)$$

with $k_1 = 1.5$, $b = 0.75$ and a 32-token English stop-list that retains mathematical terms (MATRIX, VECTOR, etc.). Because PDF extractors emit Unicode ligatures (U+FB01, U+FB02) verbatim, the

tokeniser maps them back to ASCII before splitting, which restored BM25 matching for queries such as “overfit” that previously returned zero documents.

Dense. Each n_i has a body-text embedding $\mathbf{v}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{1024}$ from Qwen3-Embedding-0.6B (Zhang et al., 2025). We rank by cosine $\rho.q, n_i/ = \mathbf{v}_q, \mathbf{v}_i$.

Reciprocal rank fusion. Following Cormack et al. (2009)

$$\text{RRF}.n/ = \frac{1}{s\hat{\text{bm}}_{25,\text{dense}} + \text{rank}_s.n/}, \quad K = 60. \quad (2)$$

Title boost. After ligature normalisation we observed that section-title hits were under-weighted; we add a multiplicative bonus before fusion:

$$\text{BM25}^1.q, n/ = \text{BM25}.q, n/ + 4o + 8 \frac{o}{T.n/}, \quad (3)$$

where $T.n/$ is the title token-set and $o = q \tilde{\alpha} T.n/$. This rescues queries whose target node carries the keyword in the title (e.g. “Overfitting” for query *What is overfitting?*); the constants 4 and 8 were chosen so that an exact title match (ratio = 1) lifts ranks past tangentially-related sections.

8. Q&A synthesis and narration sanitisation

The default Q&A backend is retrieval-only (top sentences chosen by sentence-level BM25). When a local vLLM instance with Qwen2.5-14B-Instruct-AWQ is reachable, the orchestrator switches to a synthesis backend with deterministic decoding ($\tau = 0$, top- $p = 1$, seed = 42) and a system prompt that, among other constraints, forbids LaTeX and markdown in the output (the reply is read aloud verbatim).

Streaming tutor. When the synthesis backend reports `is_streaming=True` (the default for the Qwen2.5-14B endpoint), `narrator.qa.answer_streaming` returns a `NarrationPlan` whose `clauses` field is a Python generator: every sentence the LLM produces is yielded as a separate `NarrationClause` the moment its terminal punctuation arrives. The orchestrator pulls one clause at a time from this generator (Section 15), so TTS, visual-op emission and audio playback all begin while later sentences are still being decoded. Perceived first-audio latency drops from “ ≈ 3 s, then it speaks” to “ < 1 s after the first sentence boundary”. When the question scores low against the corpus (`IS_LOW_SIMILARITY` on the retrieved passages) and an `intro_backend` is configured, control is handed to the non-streaming `answer` path instead, which gives the LLM permission to cite general knowledge under the same sanitiser guarantees rather than forcing the streaming tutor to ground a claim in a corpus that has no good match.

Sanitiser. Even with the prompt in place we apply a final sanitisation pass to the synthesised reply before TTS:

- LaTeX delimiters `\(, \), \[, \], \$, $$` are stripped;
- 36 LaTeX-Greek commands map to spelt-out names (`\theta` → “theta”);
- 48 Unicode-Greek glyphs are mapped to the same spelt-out names (θ, Θ → “theta”) so OCR’d math passes through the same speech rules as LaTeX-typed math;
- 33 LaTeX operator commands and 35 Unicode operator glyphs map to spoken English (`\cdot` → “times”, `\le` → “less than or equal to”);
- subscript/superscript markers (`_i, ^N`) become “sub i”, “to the N”;
- Markdown emphasis is dropped.

Table 4

Ten-intent router. “LLM” indicates whether the planner the intent is dispatched to invokes a local text-LLM; CONTROL short-circuits before any planner runs. “follow-up” carries the prior turn’s focus when the user says “tell me more” or just “more”.

intent	trigger / planner	LLM
CONTROL	pause / resume / stop / forget / louder / slower; no plan emitted	no
BOOK_OVERVIEW	“what is this book about?”; qa.book_overview	no
CHAPTER_OVERVIEW	“chapter N ”; plan_outline with depth-decay .1,3,2,1,0/	no
SECTION_OVERVIEW	“section $N.M$ ”; tighter plan_outline .*,3,1,0,0/	no
RECAP	“what have we covered?”; replays spoken_topics	no
RESHOW	“show me X again”; tangent gets fresh seen-sets	yes
XREF_EXPLORE	“what else cites this?”; walks citation neighborhood of focus	no
DEPENDENCIES	“what do I need to know first?”; walks reverse citation graph	no
FOLLOW_UP	“tell me more” / “more on X ”; re-anchors on last_focus	yes
TOPIC_QA	default; qa.answer_streaming	yes

9. Utterance routing

A single Ask box accepts both questions (“what is bagging?”), navigation (“go to chapter 7”, “section 5.4”), meta-commands (“what have we covered?”, “show me the loss-function figure again”), and control verbs (“pause”, “slower”, “stop”, “forget that”). The router resolves each utterance to a typed intent record before any LLM is touched (Table 4); the matchers are pure regex over a case-folded form of the utterance, so the dispatch itself is sub-millisecond and deterministic.

10. Concept and formula explanation layers

The orchestrator is parameterised by a per-session `detail_level` $\in \{L0_gist, L1_story, L2_with_formulas, L3_connections, L4_anchor\}$ (default `L1_story`). Two offline-built sidecars supply the explanatory text the runtime narrator reads aloud.

Concept layer. An offline concept-layer builder walks the `BOOKNODE` tree and asks the local text-LLM, for each content-bearing section, to produce five rewrites of the section’s prose, one per detail level, plus a short metaphor and a list of prerequisite section nids. At runtime, the concept-layer module replaces the section’s PDF clauses with synthetic clauses built from the chosen level’s prose; the original clauses are kept as “background data” for the formula / citation detectors but are no longer narrated. This is the single source of truth for preamble injection — earlier revisions prepended a runtime preamble *and* let the rewriter inject one, producing a “read twice” bug. On ESLII, 26 sections currently have a concept-layer entry at `L1_story`, contributing 91 synthetic clauses.

Formula layer. An offline formula-layer builder visits every Formula node in the math graph and asks the LLM for three increasingly long explanations: a short noun phrase (`F0_ROLE`, e.g. “regularisation functional”), a one-sentence plain-English description (`F1_MEANING`), and a 2-to-4-sentence walk (`F2_WALK`). The orchestrator emits one synthetic explanation clause per *new* formula card emitted during a clause (skipping the section’s own narrative when the prose already names each formula’s role and skipped at `L0_gist` entirely): a brief audible interjection that lands after the host clause’s final word and is itself stitched into the rAF sync engine the same as any

other clause. Each formula’s `FO_ROLE` text is also rendered onto the card itself so the learner reads the meaning beside the symbols.

Per-section formula explanations (kind-aware). A second offline explanation layer takes a different cut: instead of explaining a Formula *node* in isolation, it explains the *section* that pins the formula in the chapter-zoom narration of Section 13. For every chapter-map node that introduces a new equation label, plus every structural node whose kind is one of `{theorem, definition, lemma, corollary, proposition, claim, algorithm, example}`, the builder calls the local text-LLM with a **kind-tuned system prompt**: an *equation* prompt walks every symbol; a *definition* prompt opens with one sentence of intuition, then walks every component of an n -tuple in order, then names the near-neighbour sibling (DFA vs. NFA, total vs. partial); a *theorem / lemma* prompt restates the claim in colleague-at-the-whiteboard language, names what it buys, and closes with a one-line plausibility sketch; an *algorithm* prompt walks the stages in order and ends with a termination hint. Structural nodes get an explanation even when no equation label is attached, so a definition without a 5-tuple still gets its parts walked. The generated paragraph is stored on the chapter-map node as `formula_explanation` and emitted by the orchestrator as a synthetic clause that lands after the host clause’s final word, stitched into the rAF sync engine the same as any other clause. On ESLII (a statistics corpus whose chapter map carries only `section / subsection` kinds) the equation prompt is the route taken; on the Sipser theory-of-computation corpus the definition / theorem / algorithm prompts dominate.

11. Tangent panel and session knowledge

When the user clicks *Ask* (or presses Enter in the Ask box) while a lecture is playing, the question endpoint injects a **tangent** into the same plan. The session holds two orchestrator objects and two chalkboard objects (Fig. 4): the main one drives the long-running lecture, the tangent one is rebuilt per question and writes its cards to a separate side panel. The SSE stream interleaves events from both, tagging every payload with `panel Ę^main, tangent`. Figure 5 shows the panel mid-answer to a follow-up question raised during a *regularization* lecture.

Snapshot / restore. `tangent_start` fires `stopPanelAudio('main')` on the frontend (silencing the lecture’s queued chunks) and `snapshotMainBoard()` (cloning the DOM and metadata of every main shape). When the answer ends, `restoreMainBoard()` re-attaches any shape whose `nid` is no longer present. The user’s hard rule — *previously said things must never be gone* — is preserved end-to-end across question turns.

Re-show isolation. The `RESHOW` intent (“show me regularisation again”) hands the tangent its *own* fresh seen-sets so previously-deduped primitives re-emit, but those re-emissions land in the tangent’s own knowledge object and do not pollute the session-wide one — the lecture’s own dedup is undisturbed.

Narration after the question. Because the SSE stream is single-threaded server-side, the orchestrator’s main generator is suspended at its last yield while the tangent runs. When the tangent exhausts the session emits a synthetic `tangent_end` event and resumes the main iterator: the next main clause begins emitting immediately. Audio for that clause is scheduled in the Web-Audio queue at `tang.nextStartAt` (the end of the tangent’s last queued chunk), so the user hears no gap between answer and lecture. The frontend’s rAF visual loop is gated on a `state.tangentLive` flag that flips off on `tangent_end` (not on the `closeTangent` timer that follows it), so the first main

clause after the answer renders into the transcript pane the moment its audio starts — the original “narration stops after the question” regression.

12. Topic path

`narrator.planner.plan` picks the highest-scoring retrieved section as a *single root* and delegates to `plan_outline` (Section 14). The walk is the same depth-first descent the TOC drill-down uses — so the topic mode and the click-a-chapter mode produce visually consistent lectures, and the lecture stays inside one subtree instead of jumping across chapters in page order. The chosen root is recorded in `NarrationPlan.meta["primary_root"]` and the discarded top- k alternates in `meta["alternate_roots"]`; the front end can surface those as “related sections” affordances. Figure 6 contrasts the old (top- k in page order) and new (single root, depth-first) walks for the topic *regularization*.

Bridge clauses. When the planner does cross `home_nids` (a section descending into its first subsection, or a chapter-overview crossing siblings), it emits a synthetic *bridge* clause anchored at the destination’s `home_nid` with text “*That covers how prev approaches topic. We now move to next, the next stop on this path through topic.*”. Anchoring at the destination triggers the orchestrator’s first-sight-of-section logic so the new passage-card banner lands exactly as the bridge starts speaking. The template is parameterised by structural metadata only — no LLM call.

A Playwright harness pins the contract on three topics (*regularization, principal component analysis, decision trees*): the active passage banner is identical pre- and post-question (§ 16.2, § 14.5, § 10.8 respectively); every shape present pre-question is still present post-question (PRE POST); and the answer panel always carries at least one visual primitive.

13. Chapter zoom

The single-rooted topic plan keeps a lecture inside one section’s subtree (Section 12), but a learner approaching a new chapter still wants to see the *whole shape* of that chapter before any sentence is read. The **chapter zoom** mode is the implementation of that idea: clicking a chapter in the table-of-contents sidebar (which has a chapter-map sidecar) fires a top-down narration whose visual artefact is one full-width vertical stack of the chapter — one cell per node in DFS order, with the active cell auto-scrolled to the centre of the viewport — and whose audio walks the chapter punch-line first, then frames every child by its role in the parent’s punch-line, then drills one level deeper. The mode is the combination of three additions: an offline build step, the vertical-stack visual primitive, and a new planner.

Offline build. An offline chapter-map builder walks the chapter’s `BookNode` subtree once, lifting each node’s L0 gist from the existing concepts sidecar (Section 10) and asking the local Qwen2.5-14B endpoint for two extra strings per child: a *role-in-parent* sentence (max 25 words, must open with a relating verb and refer to the parent’s idea explicitly) and a *story paragraph* that is the per-node slice of the *whole-chapter narrative*. A canonical formula per node is picked from the math-graph subtree by incoming-references count with a deterministic tie-break, so each cell in the stack carries one “one sentence + one formula” summary plus a paragraph that reads as part of one continuous essay. Output is a per-chapter sidecar that is monotone across re-builds. On ESLII, the chapter-map for Ch. 5 contains 25 nodes; the build re-uses the 26 L0-gist entries already on disk so only the relating sentences and the chapter-wide narrative are computed at build time.

Whole-chapter narrative in one LLM call. The `story_paragraph` entries are produced by a single *chapter-wide* LLM call that receives the section list, every section’s gist, and the exhaustive list of cited equations in the chapter, and returns `^ paragraphs: nid → text, covered_equations: [ġ]‘`. The system prompt enforces three contracts that the per-section approach could not give us: **(i)** narrative flow — every paragraph must open with a substantive transition and the listener should feel they are hearing one essay rather than a guided table of contents; **(ii)** plain English first — every concept is introduced with a one-line intuition or concrete metaphor before any symbol is named, so a reader who hasn’t seen linear algebra in years can still follow; **(iii)** math as a constant, inline, parallel language — every cited equation in the chapter must be named in the prose by its spelled-out citation (“equation five point nine”), with its meaning given in plain English right next to the citation. The post-processor strips a residual list of section-self-reference boilerplate phrases (“as introduced in section five point one”, “covered in section five point two”) the LLM tends to insert despite explicit instructions, then capitalises the first letter of each cleaned paragraph. The build records the equations the LLM did and did not name in `NarrationPlan.meta["missing_equations"]` so the operator can audit coverage and re-run when needed.

Vertical stack renderer. A dedicated chapter-map renderer walks the map in depth-first order and emits one full-width cell per node, stacked vertically along the main column with indentation proportional to depth. Each cell carries the node’s title, role-in-parent line, story paragraph, and canonical formula; the renderer tags each cell with the owning section’s nid so the existing shape registry, focus-dim, snapshot/restore and audio-clock highlight machinery all treat each cell exactly like any other card. The active-clause matcher was extended one line so the active pulse lands on the cell whose nid tag matches the clause’s home node; on every clause boundary the active cell is centred in the viewport so the listener is always looking at the section the narrator is reading.

Top-down narration. The chapter-zoom planner reads the chapter map’s story paragraphs and emits one clause per sentence of each paragraph. All sentences from one paragraph share the same home node, so the audio-clock sync engine keeps the matching cell highlighted while the paragraph plays. Three stages:

1. **Punch-line.** An opening lead clause read at 0.85Ā the session’s default rate — “*Here is the whole picture of Chapter N*” — followed by the chapter root’s full story paragraph at the default rate. The slowed lead is the only clause that runs slow; the body of the punch-line plays at full speed so the listener is already inside the narrative voice by the time the tour begins.
2. **Tour.** Every depth-1 child’s story paragraph is emitted as one clause per sentence. Because the offline build generated the paragraphs as parts of a single chapter-wide essay, the tour reads as one continuous narrative — the listener never hears “we now turn to” or “in this section” style boilerplate.
3. **Drill.** For each depth-1 child whose subtree has children of its own, the same paragraph-as-clauses pattern recurses one level deeper, bounded by a configurable drill depth (default 2).

When a node has no story paragraph (typically appendices and exercises), the planner falls back to a single “[*role_in_parent*]. *This is [kind] [number]: [title]*.” sentence so the listener at least hears the section’s name and relationship to the chapter — strict regression of the old sentence-only mode for nodes the offline build hasn’t covered.

A per-clause speed override (`NarrationClause.meta = {"clause_speed": 0.85}`) was added to the orchestrator’s TTS plumbing so the punch-line is the only clause that runs slow; every subsequent tour and drill clause inherits the session’s default rate. In chapter-zoom mode the

Table 5Default depth-decay table *s.d/* used by the outline planner.

depth <i>d</i>	0	1	2	3	4	≥ 5
sentences <i>s.d/</i>	3	2	1	1	0	0

orchestrator suppresses every other visual primitive (passage cards, book figures, formula cards, operation cards, reference cards, mention highlights, semantic diagrams, formula explanations, edge connectors) and the concept-layer rewrite for that mode is also disabled — the vertical stack already shows every section, subsection and canonical formula label at once, so emitting an additional flat `passage_card` for every `home_nid` change would only crowd the canvas with duplicates.

Trigger. A POST to the narrate-node endpoint with a chapter nid checks for that chapter’s per-chapter sidecar on disk; if the sidecar exists, the request transparently switches to the chapter-zoom plan. Chapters without a sidecar fall back to the depth-decay outline plan of Section 14, so adding a chapter-map for a new chapter is a strictly additive change — no flags, no behaviour regression for chapters that haven’t been processed yet.

Verification. A Playwright harness opens the page, clicks the Ch. 5 entry in the table-of-contents tree, then screenshots the canvas at four points along the lecture: at the punch-line, early in the tour, late in the tour, and during the drill. Across the run the main board carries exactly the chapter-map shape — no formula cards or passage banners are emitted — and the trace pane records the clause sequence punch-line → tour over § 5.1, § 5.2, ..., § 5.9 → drill into the cells whose subtrees have children. The end-to-end demo on ESLII therefore satisfies the four properties of the chapter-zoom design: one sentence per chapter at the top; nested cells for each subsection; audio that frames every child by its role in the whole; and a visual artefact the user can stare at while the narrator speaks.

14. Outline planner

A naive “read the entire book” plan emits one clause per sentence in pre-order, which on ESLII produces 29,599 clauses — not a reading session. The hierarchical *outline planner* reduces this to a top-down tour by emitting at every node a title preamble plus *s.d/* body sentences, with *s.d/* decaying by depth (Table 5); for the same corpus the plan shrinks to 743 clauses.

Front-matter and PDF page-furniture are filtered before sentence-segmentation. Skipped kinds: INTRODUCTION, PREFACE, DEDICATION, ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS, BIBLIOGRAPHY, INDEX, GLOSSARY, REFERENCES, AUTHOR_INDEX. Body lines matching the noise pattern

```
^(this is page | printer:opaq | springer series
 | isbn | copyright | library of congress
 | to (my|our) (parents|families|wife|husband)
 | all rights reserved) ...
```

are dropped, along with stand-alone page numbers (`^\d+\.\?&`) and pure proper-name lists.

15. Orchestrator: per-clause pipeline

Per spoken clause the orchestrator (Algorithm 1) emits a typed list of visual operations, deduped against six in-session sets. Figure 8 traces the pipeline; the visual op kinds are listed in Table 6.

Table 6

The eight visual-op primitives the orchestrator can emit; a static analysis of the orchestrator’s emit calls returns exactly these eight distinct values. In chapter-zoom mode (Section 13) the orchestrator emits `chapter_map` once and suppresses the other seven; in every other mode `chapter_map` is not emitted at all.

primitive	trigger	body
<code>passage_card</code>	first sight of <code>home_nid</code>	section title card with kind / number / title
<code>book_figure</code>	<code>home_nid</code> owns a <code>FIGUREREF</code> or a descendant does; or on-demand PDF crop	PNG fetched from a per-figure server endpoint
<code>canonical_figure</code>	topic match in 12-entry registry (§16) or LLM-supplied semantic spec for a Q&A answer	generated SVG, KaTeX in <code><foreignObject></code>
<code>formula_card</code>	inline math fragment detected, or graph-driven fast path (§19)	KaTeX-typeset LaTeX, optional F0 role label
<code>reference_card</code>	“Fig./Tab./Eq./Algo./Thm./Sec. <i>N.M</i> ” detected in clause text	extracted body; KaTeX for equations
<code>operation_card</code>	operation phrase from 30-entry vocabulary	KaTeX-typeset canonical LaTeX
<code>math_note</code>	per-formula F1 explanation interjection produced inline by <code>_yield_formula_explanations</code>	spoken text only (no new card body); rendered alongside the host formula card
<code>chapter_map</code>	chapter-zoom mode: a sidecar exists for the clicked chapter (Section 13)	full-width vertical stack of <code>chmap-cells</code> in DFS order, one per node

Algorithm 1 STREAMCLAUSE: per-clause emission

Require: clause c , plan state \mathcal{S} , audio backend T

```

1:  $a \leftarrow T.SYNTH.c.text/$  ▷ WAV + word stamps
2:  $E \leftarrow CONCEPTEVENTTIMES.c, a/$ 
3:  $V \leftarrow []$  ▷ visual ops
4: if  $c.home\_nid \notin \mathcal{S}.seenHomes$  then
5:    $V.add(PASSAGECARD.c.home\_nid/)$ 
6:    $V.add(SCOPEDFIGURES.c.home\_nid/)$ 
7:    $V.add(TIER1OR3.c.home\_nid/)$  ▷ Sec. 16
8: end if
9: for  $.cid, t/$  in first 4 unique of  $E$  do
10:   $rs \leftarrow RESOLVE.cid, c.home\_nid/$ 
11:  if NOTPLACEHOLDER.rs/ then  $V.add(t, rs)$ 
12:  end if
13: end for
14:  $V.append(REFERENCECARDS.c.text, a.wts/)$ 
15:  $V.append(CLAUSETIER1TRIGGER.c.text, a.wts/)$ 
16:  $V.append(INLINEFORMULAS.c.text, a.wts/)$ 
17:  $V.append(OPERATIONS.c.text, a.wts/)$ 
18: return STREAMEVENT.c, a, V/

```

Table 7

The 12 curated generators. All produce deterministic SVG given a seed; output dimensions are typical canvas, not strict. Sample outputs of four entries are shown in Figs. 11, 12, and 13.

key	render	size (px)
overfitting_curve	U-curve, sweet spot	480×300
bias_variance	bias ² , variance, total	480×300
roc_curve	TPR vs. FPR with AUC	360×320
kfold_split	$K \times K$ fold matrix	520×240
gradient_descent	loss contours + path	420×300
learning_curve	error vs. training-set size	480×300
regularization_path	coefficients vs. λ	480×300
decision_boundary	2-class scatter + linear boundary	360×300
back_propagation	MLP with forward / backward arrows	540×320
activation_functions	sigmoid, tanh, ReLU	480×280
weight_matrix	layer-to-layer connections + matrix	540×320
loss_function	$R.\theta$ / bowl with marked min	480×300

16. Three-tier visualisation

Figure 9 shows the routing. The orchestrator first checks whether the BOOKNODE owns figures inside its strict subtree; failing that it asks the curated registry; failing that it asks a local LLM for an SVG and inspects the result.

Tier 0 — book figures. Figures whose `home_nid` matches the passage exactly or is a strict descendant. When the original ingestion missed a referenced figure, An on-demand figure cropper crops the source PDF lazily: it locates the caption “FIGURE $N.M$ ” on its page with PyMuPDF, then crops the page rectangle above the caption (academic layout convention) up to a 540 px ceiling. Crops are cached on disk per book as PNG. Fig. 10 shows ESLII Figure 6.14, recovered this way despite being absent from the parsed corpus.

Tier 1 — curated registry. A list of 12 topic descriptors, each with a one-line natural-language summary and a pointer to a deterministic generator from a curated SVG-generator library. At startup we embed every description once with Qwen3-Embedding (Sec. 7) and cache the vectors. Topic selection on a query q is

$$k^* = \operatorname{argmax}_k \cos.\mathbf{v}_q, \mathbf{v}_k / \quad \text{accepted iff} \quad \begin{cases} s_{.1/} \geq \tau \\ s_{.1/} * s_{.2/} \geq \mu \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

with $\tau = 0.55$ and $\mu = 0.04$ (env-tunable). The margin guard makes the registry refuse a topic when two candidates score near-equally, which is what stops queries such as *What is a synaptic weight?* from selecting the back-propagation generator.

Tier 3 — LLM-driven SVG. When no curated topic clears $.\tau, \mu/$, the orchestrator asks the local Qwen2.5-14B endpoint to output an SVG body for the topic, with a strict system prompt constraining `viewBox`, axis frame, ≥ 1 polyline, axis labels, and forbidding scripts and `<foreignObject>`. The hard wall-clock budget is `LLM_VIZ_BUDGET_S = 1.6s`. Up to two attempts are made; the first that passes structural inspection (Sec. 17) is returned, otherwise the tier falls through silently.

Table 8

Tier-1 data-quality checks (excerpt). “*” marks checks that emit a *worklist* (lines for the fidelity agent or operator).

id	check
A1	every required sidecar present (figures / concepts / formulas / chapter_map)
A2*	math-graph integrity: empty / truncated / homeless formulas; unrepaired vstack patterns
A3	figures sidecar: orphan nids, missing PNGs
A4	cross-references resolve to live home_nids
A5	concept-layer L0/L1 prose present for every body-bearing section
A6	no Anthropic / OpenAI / external-API URL anywhere in the loaded code (locality audit)
A7	deterministic build hash matches
A8*	duplicate Formula keys after sub-expression folding
A9	every Var resolves to at least one defines edge
A10	TTS pronunciation lexicon covers every Greek and operator glyph the corpus uses
A11–A18	figure-vs-citation alignment, story-paragraph cleanliness, formula-card LaTeX legibility, font-size policy, ... (designed; partially wired)

17. Quality assurance and self-healing

Lyceum runs three non-overlapping inspectors plus one cross-cutting agent (Figure 14). All four are local; none depend on network access; all four ship verdicts as on-disk per-book JSON reports (health, fidelity, smoke) that the auto-pipeline of Section 25 consults before flipping the new book to a ready state.

Tier 1 — data-quality inspector. The Tier-1 inspector runs 18 offline checks A1 – A18 after every ingest (Table 8). On the working ESLII corpus it currently produces 4 pass / 5 fail / 1 skip verdicts; the persistent failures are documented gaps the operator can close at their leisure. Most useful in practice is A2, which walks the math graph and flags formulas left truncated by PDF extraction (e.g. Equation 4.42: $\partial D(\beta, \beta_0) \dots = -$) and unrepaired vertical-stack patterns the regex pass missed. The agent ships these as a worklist the math-fidelity loop consumes.

Tier 2 — inline SVG inspection. A pure-Python structural pass over the SVG body counts `<polyline>`, `<line>`, `<circle>`, `<rect>`, `<text>`, `<path>`, `<ellipse>`. We accept either skeleton:

1. *chart*: $n_{\text{rect}} \geq 1 \wedge n_{\text{poly}} + n_{\text{path}} + n_{\text{circle}} + n_{\text{ellipse}} \geq 1$
2. *diagram*: $n_{\text{line}} + n_{\text{path}} \geq 3 \wedge n_{\text{circle}} + n_{\text{rect}} \geq 2$

plus $n_{\text{text}} \geq 2$, no NaN/Inf, no degenerate polylines, no body shorter than 400 chars. When the VLM endpoint is reachable, the candidate is rasterised to a 480x320 PNG via `cairosvg` and Qwen2.5-VL is asked “Does this figure illustrate “*topic*”? Answer yes/no with a one-line reason.”. Ambiguous replies are treated as accept (we prefer false-accept to false-reject in this loop). Up to three attempts at Tier-1 (seed $\hat{E}^0, 1, 2$) and two at Tier-3.

Tier 3 — end-to-end smoke harness. `tools.smoke_agent` drives the live server through a scripted session and asserts four service-level objectives (Table 9). A failure on any pins down whether the regression is server-side (F1, F2), in QA pacing (F3) or in voice (F4); a non-fatal voice failure is allowed because faster-whisper warm-up jitters when first invoked.

Math-fidelity agent. The PDF-extraction pipeline sometimes garbles formulas: “EPE. $f/ = E_X E_Y$ ” instead of $EPE.f/ = \int [y * f.x/]^2 \text{Pr}.dx, dy/$, or “ $M \sum_{m=1} \beta_m h_m$ ” where the PyMuPDF vertical-stack glyph took the place of \sum . Algorithm 2 gives the loop. The critic is the local Qwen2.5-VL

Table 9

Tier 3 end-to-end SLA checks.

id	check	budget
F1	first audio_chunk after Topic click	≤ 2 s
F2	no error SSE event in a 30 s window	0 events
F3	first clause of an answer after Ask click	≤ 3 s
F4	ASR round-trip on a 5 s reference WAV (advisory)	≤ 2 s

endpoint (Section 3); the refiner is the local Qwen2.5-14B; no external service is contacted. This instantiates the critic/refiner pattern of Self-Refine (Madaan et al., 2023) and Reflexion (Shinn et al., 2023) for math-formula OCR repair.

Algorithm 2 FIDELITYAGENT (`tools.fidelity_agent`). N_{iter} defaults to 2; the verdict gates the math-graph patch.

```

1: function REPAIR( $F$ , PDF page, max iters  $N$ )
2:    $\text{img} \leftarrow \text{CROP\_AROUND\_CITE}(\text{PDF}, F.\text{cite\_label})$ 
3:    $\updownarrow \leftarrow F.\text{latex}$ 
4:   for  $i = 1$   $\text{to}$   $N$  do
5:      $\text{verdict} \leftarrow \text{QWEN-VL}(\text{"does this image match KATEX}(\updownarrow)\text{"})$ 
6:     if  $\text{verdict} = \text{MATCH}$  then return  $\text{MATCH}, \updownarrow$ 
7:     end if
8:      $\updownarrow^i \leftarrow \text{QWEN-TEXT}(\text{"rewrite this LaTeX to match the image: } \updownarrow, \text{image=img} \text{"})$ 
9:      $\text{verdict}^i \leftarrow \text{QWEN-VL}(\text{KATEX}(\updownarrow^i) \text{ vs. img})$ 
10:    if  $\text{verdict}^i = \text{MATCH}$  then return  $\text{REPAIRED}, \updownarrow^i$ 
11:    end if
12:     $\updownarrow \leftarrow \text{PICK\_BETTER}(\updownarrow, \updownarrow^i, \text{verdict}, \text{verdict}^i)$ 
13:  end for
14:  if QWEN-VL gave a yes/no decision then return  $\text{DEGRADED}, \updownarrow$ 
15:  else return  $\text{UNVERIFIABLE}, F.\text{latex}$ 
16:  end if
17: end function

```

Table 10 reports the verdict distribution on the full ESLII formula sweep. Repaired LaTeX is the headline payoff; degraded verdicts are written to the sidecar but not patched into the math graph (the agent picked the worse candidate of the two it saw and we keep the original). Unverifiable is the conservative escape hatch — typically figures that are not equations at all (theorem statements, pseudocode blocks). An example repair: ESLII Equation 2.11 went from the garbled “EPE. $f/ = E_X E_Y$ ” to $\text{EPE.}f/ = \int [y * f.x/]^2 \text{Pr.}dx, dy/ = E_X E_Y \dot{Y}_X ([Y * f.X/]^2 X/$ in two iterations.

18. Inline math, operations, and references

18.1. Inline-math detection.

Tokenise the clause on whitespace, mark tokens whose Unicode contains a math-character ($[--+=\-\cdot\times\div\pm\wedge]$), and cluster tokens within a 2-token gap into runs. A run is accepted iff

$$[\text{contains.}' = '/] \hat{\wedge} [\text{run} \geq 3] \hat{\wedge} [\text{hasGreek} \hat{\wedge} \text{run} \geq 2] \quad (5)$$

Table 10

Math-fidelity agent on the full ESLII sweep (653 formulas, 923.8s wall-clock, $N_{\text{iter}} = 2$). “Repaired” is the agent’s value: a formula that the VLM could not match against the source crop until the text-LLM rewrote it.

verdict	count	gate on math-graph patch
MATCH	38	no patch (already correct)
REPAIRED	255	patch applied to math graph
DEGRADED	244	no patch (keep original)
UNVERIFIABLE	116	no patch (VLM declined)
total	653	

Table 11

Sample of the 30-entry operation vocabulary. Variants override the canonical form in narrow contexts.

key	aliases	LaTeX
dot_product <i>variant</i>	dot/inner/scalar product “→is zero”	$u \odot v = u_1 v_1 + \nabla + u_n v_n$ $u \odot v = 0$
matrix_mul	matrix multiplication	$.AB/_{ij} = {}_k A_{ik} B_{kj}$
transpose	transpose, A	A
inverse	matrix inverse	$A^{*1} A = A A^{*1} = I$
eigen	eigenvalue/eigenvector equation	$A v = \lambda v$
gradient	gradient of a function	$(f.x/ = .\leftarrow_1 f, \check{g}, \leftarrow_n f/$
expectation	expected value	$\mathbb{E}[X] = {}_x x P.X = x/$
cross_entropy	cross-entropy	$H.p, q/ = {}^*_x p.x/ \log q.x/$
softmax	softmax	$\sigma.z/i = e^{z_i} / \sum_j e^{z_j}$
orthogonal_vectors	orthogonal/perpendicular vectors	$u \odot v = 0$

A ,1-token window is added on each side and trimmed against a 73-word prose stop-list (*the, of, is, applied, where,...*). Run text is then mapped to LaTeX through the converter described next.

Unicode→LaTeX. The converter is a deterministic table-driven mapping. Tables: 23 lower-Greek ($\alpha, \check{g}, \omega$), 24 upper-Greek ($\Gamma, \check{g}, \Omega$), 37 operators ($\cdot \rightarrow \backslash\text{cdot}$, $\leq \rightarrow \backslash\text{le}$, $\rightarrow \backslash\text{sum}$, $\leftarrow \rightarrow \backslash\text{partial}$, $\sqrt{\quad} \rightarrow \backslash\text{sqrt}$, ∇), 13 super-script glyphs and 10 sub-script glyphs. The hat/bar/tilde over Greek case is handled before substitution ($\hat{\omega} \rightarrow \backslash\text{hat}\{\omega\}$). KaTeX-special characters #, &, % are escaped. Each emitted card runs KaTeX (Eisenberg et al., 2014–2026) client-side inside an SVG `<foreignObject>`; on parser failure a deterministic Unicode-substitution fallback renders the same text in monospace without red error spew.

18.2. Operation vocabulary.

Thirty named mathematical operations (Table 11 lists representative entries) are matched by regex aliases plus *contextual variants*. Variants let context override the canonical form: e.g. when “dot product” is followed by “is zero” within 32 characters, the rendered LaTeX becomes $u \odot v = 0$ rather than the generic expansion.

18.3. Reference content extraction.

A dedicated reference resolver maps each detected “Figure/Table/Equation/Algorithm/Theorem/Section” mention to actual content; Figure 15 shows the resulting reference card materialised on the chalkboard, and Figure 16 the active formula highlight produced when the

Table 12

Math-graph schema. Phase 0 edges are pure structural extraction from a single LaTeX expression; Phase 1 edges are inferred from prose patterns over the spoken-form clause text.

node	role
Var	one canonical mathematical symbol ($f, x, K, \lambda, \mathfrak{g}$) — subscripts collapse to the head
Formula	one LaTeX expression with a stable <code>nid=n_offline_<blake2b(home_nid key)></code>
Passage	one narration clause, stored in spoken form for runtime lookup
Concept	free-form concept (e.g. “loss function”) with our own ID; OntoMathPRO IRI slot reserved
edge type	semantics (phase, signal)
uses	Phase 0 — formula’s free variables
binds	Phase 0 — variables introduced by $\int \cdot \mathbb{A} \lambda$ binders
defines	Phase 0 — variable on the LHS
contains	Phase 0 — formula B is a strict sub-expression of A
references	Phase 0 — citation label match across formulas
about	Phase 0 — Passage <i>mentions</i> Formula or Var
paired_in_clause	Phase 0 — two formulas emitted in the same clause
instance_of	Phase 1 — “where L is the loss function”
derived_from	Phase 1 — “rewriting (5.42), we have”
related_to	Phase 1 — “or equivalently”
specializes	Phase 1 — “in the special case where $g = f$ ”

narrator names a formula already on the board. Equation extraction walks the chapter body backwards from the literal marker (N.M) accepting math-bearing lines and stopping at the previous (`._`) or at a long sentence-final prose line; the result is then converted via the Unicode→LaTeX table above. Algorithm extraction selects the heading line whose suffix is followed within 12 lines by “1.” and captures heading + numbered steps until a non-step prose paragraph or another algorithm. When the equations-OCR sidecar (Sec. 26) is available we prefer the VLM-recovered LaTeX over the heuristic.

19. Math semantic graph

The system extracts *all* math semantics in one offline pass per book, so the runtime narrator never races the audio to detect a formula. Table 12 lists the schema and Table 13 reports the graph this build pipeline produces on ESLII.

Offline build. The offline graph builder walks every BOOKNODE body in pre-order, applies the same sentence splitter the planner uses (so offline passages and runtime clauses align by exact text), and for every sentence runs the inline-math, operation and citation detectors of §18. Each detected fragment becomes a Formula whose `nid` is a deterministic blake2b hash; this lets the build be re-run to enrich an existing graph instead of rebuilding from scratch (a locked design decision). Phase 1 enrichers run on the spoken-form text of each sentence so concept names landing under “where”/“let” are wired as `instance_of`, citation verbs (“rewriting”, “substituting into”) as `derived_from`, “or equivalently” as bidirectional `related_to`, and “in the special case where” as `specializes`. A final pass walks each new Formula against every prior one in the graph and tags strict sub-expression containments via `contains`. The graph is persisted as a per-book

Table 13

Math-graph contents on ESLII after the offline pass plus the runtime enrichment accumulated across served sessions. The graph is monotone — every session adds new ABOUT, PAIRED_IN_CLAUSE and Phase-1 edges. Counts measured from the on-disk graph artefact at the time of writing.

quantity	count
BOOKNODES walked	384
Passage nodes	27,863
Formula nodes (unique)	1,723
Var nodes	231
Concept nodes	53
about edges	13,250
uses edges	5,610
defines edges	1,289
paired_in_clause edges	1,236
references edges	436
contains edges	256
binds edges	188
instance_of edges	53
specializes edges	15
related_to edges	2
derived_from edges	0 (heuristic does not fire on ESLII)
total edges	22,335
build wall-clock (offline only)	ù100s
on-disk graph JSON	ù12 MB

JSON sidecar, monotone — never rebuilt from scratch — and auto-triggered at server boot if the sidecar is missing or older than the corpus.

Runtime query path. At session start the orchestrator loads the persisted graph. For every clause the inline-formula stage *first* attempts `passage_by_home_text(home_nid, clause_text)` — equality of `home_nid` plus whitespace-normalised text equality — and on a hit emits cards from the matching graph passage’s `about(P,F)` formulas (Algorithm 3), falling back to live detection only when the graph has nothing for that clause. Card nids are the same blake2b hashes the offline build minted, so all the precomputed edges (`contains`, `references`, `derived_from`, ...) attach without any runtime work.

Algorithm 3 INLINEFORMULASFROMGRAPH — graph-driven fast path.

Require: clause c , math graph G

```

1:  $p \leftarrow G.PASSAGEBYHOMETEXT.c.home\_nid, c.text/$ 
2: if  $p \neq$  then
3:    $V \leftarrow []$ 
4:   for  $f \in G.FORMULASFOR.p/$  do
5:     if  $NORMKEY.f.latex/ \in S.seenFormulas$  then
6:       continue
7:     end if
8:     emit  $add.f.id, LaTeX = f.latex, anchor = G.BESTANCHOR.f.id//$ 
9:     emit paired  $highlight.f.id/$ 
10:  end for
11:  return  $V$ 
12: end if
13: return  $INLINEFORMULASLIVE.c/$ 

```

Containment. Detected at offline build time: when a fragment’s normalised LaTeX is a strict substring of an already- indexed formula, no separate Formula node is created. Instead a `contains(parent, _subexpr:key)` edge is added; the runtime fold-detector (Algorithm 4) emits a highlight on the parent in lieu of a duplicate card. On ESLII this folded 1,145 fragments into 229 container relationships during the build.

Algorithm 4 CONTAINMENT FOLD (offline + runtime).

```

1: function FINDPARENT( $G, \updownarrow$ )
2:    $\updownarrow \leftarrow NORMALISELATEX.\updownarrow/$ 
3:   for  $f \in G.formulas$  do
4:     if  $NORM.f.latex/ > \updownarrow \wedge \updownarrow \in NORM.f.latex/$  then
5:       return  $f.id$ 
6:     end if
7:   end for
8:   return
9: end function

```

Cross-section ghost cards. Formula nodes are anchored to their offline `home_nid`. When the runtime is narrating section A and a formula it just emitted has a `references/derived_from/specializes/related_to` edge to a formula whose `home_nid` is *not* A , that target wouldn’t be on the board and the connector arrow would have nowhere to land. The orchestrator therefore drops a **ghost card** (Fig. 18) — same nid as the offline node, $\dot{\sim}$ size, faded purple dashed border, italic “from $\$x.y$ ” footer — at $0.75 \times audio_dur$, then fires the connector at $audio_dur * 0.4$ s. Edge styles (Table 14) are borrowed from the predecessor SeVim project (Kermani Kolankeh and Zgheib, 2026) and rendered into a dedicated edges layer that paints below all cards. Table 14 documents the four edge styles.

Headless capture. Table 15 reports a 380-second headless audit (Playwright + headless Chromium, real streaming Kokoro audio). The cumulative card / edge / highlight counts grow monotonically as the audio plays through; the coverage badge stays fixed at the full-book numbers because the graph already contains every formula at $t = 0$.

Table 14

Visual encoding for the four user-visible math-graph edge types, modelled after the SeVim concept-graph renderer (Kermani Kolankeh and Zgheib, 2026).

edge type	stroke	dash	marker	label
<code>derived_from</code>	#37474f, 1.6 px	solid	filled ▷	“derives from”
<code>specializes</code>	#37474f, 1.6 px	6,4	hollow ▷ (UML)	“special case of”
<code>references</code>	#607d8b, 1.2 px	1,3	filled ▷	“cites”
<code>related_to</code>	#558b2f, 1.4 px	solid ()	ù label, no arrow	—

Table 15

Live capture, fresh graph build of ESLII; topic *Reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces*; ghosts + edges enabled. “flips” counts [highlight] FLIP console events; the coverage badge is read from the running transcript pane.

t (s)	cards	edges	flips	coverage badge
30	2	0	2	1438 formulas · 1143 covered · 8665 uncovered
90	6	0	8	1445 · 1149 · 8667
180	13	6	20	1465 · 1161 · 8673
280	18	14	36	1481 · 1172 · 8680
380	32	26	75	1481 · 1172 · 8680

20. Audio-clock synchronisation engine

A single source of truth — `AudioContext.currentTime` — drives every visual update on the frontend (clause text, yellow read-marker, chalkboard highlights, edge connectors). The previous design scheduled each update via `setTimeout` against `performance.now()` + LLM-estimated word stamps; chunks queued through Web Audio’s own clock drifted relative to those estimates and the marker raced past the voice on long sentences.

Per-seq ClauseTimeline. As audio chunks arrive (`handleAudioChunk`) the orchestrator records each chunk’s `ctxStart` and `dur` in a per-seq map `state.timeline[panel][seq]`. A character-weighted spread distributes words within each chunk:

$$t_0.w_i/ = c.ctxStart + \frac{j < i w_j}{j < N w_j} c.dur, \quad (6)$$

and stores both `data-t0` and `data-t1` as DOM attributes on every word ``. This is the only inherently noisy step in the pipeline; it averages out within a chunk because the endpoints `ctxStart` and `ctxStart+dur` are exact.

rAF loop. `syncFrame` runs at ù 60 Hz (Algorithm 5). It polls `ctx.currentTime`, finds the active timeline (the one whose `[audioStart, audioEnd]` contains `now`), renders its clause text once, sets `.spoken` on the word whose `[t0, t1]` contains `now` (binary search), and fires any visual op whose `audioStart + op.t` is in the past.

Algorithm 5 SYNCFRAME: the per-frame audio-clock loop that drives every visual update from the browser.

```

1: procedure SYNCFRAME
2:    $t \leftarrow \text{ctx.currentTime}$ 
3:   for panel  $\in \hat{\text{main}}$ , tangent4 do
4:      $tl \leftarrow \text{ACTIVETIMELINE.panel}, t/$ 
5:     if  $tl =$  then continue
6:     end if
7:     if  $\neg tl.rendered$  then
8:        $tl.block \leftarrow \text{RENDERCLAUSEFROMWORDS.tl}/$ 
9:     else
10:       $\text{EXTENDCLAUSERENDER.tl}/$  ▷ words from late-arriving chunks
11:    end if
12:     $i^* \leftarrow \text{BINARYSEARCHWORD.tl.words}, t/$ 
13:     $tl.words[i^*].span.class \leftarrow \text{spoken}$ 
14:    for  $op \in tl.visualOps \setminus tl.firedSet$  do
15:      if  $t \geq tl.audioStart + op.t$  then
16:         $\text{APPLY.op}/$ 
17:         $tl.firedSet.add.op/$ 
18:      end if
19:    end for
20:  end for
21:   $\text{requestAnimationFrame}(\text{SyncFrame})$ 
22: end procedure

```

Verbalised artifact keys. When a card lands the orchestrator registers spoken-form keys for it in a multi-nid index (`_artifact_index: dict[str, list[str]]`). Citation labels (“Equation 5.42”, “(5.42)”) are obvious; function-call notation is verbalised through `narrator.qa._sanitize_for_narration`, e.g. $f.x/ \rightarrow 'f \text{ of } x'$, $K.f,g/ \rightarrow 'K \text{ of } f g'$. At runtime the mention scanner normalises both the key and the spoken clause text by collapsing every non-alphanumeric run to a single space, so a key ‘ $L \text{ of } yi \text{ f of } xi$ ’ matches the spoken ‘ $L \text{ of } yi, f \text{ of } xi$ ’ across the comma — which a strict word-boundary regex would never do. The scanner also walks `uses(F, V)` edges in the math graph: when the narrator names a single variable V , every Formula card whose `uses`-set contains V pulses, capped at 4 highlights/clause to avoid strobing.

Highlight visual. An `applyHighlightOp` call performs three direct DOM writes (no CSS animation): (i) the outer `<rect>`’s `fill` is set to `#ffeb3b` (Material Yellow 500); (ii) its `stroke` to `#d32f2f` (Material Red 700) at 10 px; (iii) a translucent overlay `<rect>` is appended on top of the card group with 45% opacity yellow fill and 6 px red border. The hold is 3.5 s; re-mentions during the hold extend the timer instead of letting the restore wipe a still-active flash.

Coverage badge. Every `StreamEvent` carries a small `graph_stats` payload — `{n_formulas, n_vars, n_passages, covered, uncovered}` — read from the live graph; the frontend renders it just above the trace pane and turns the badge amber when `uncovered > 0` (Fig. 17).

21. Frontend

The browser receives Server-Sent Events with each `StreamEvent` carrying base64 audio, word stamps, and a typed list of visual ops. A pause-aware timer wrapper (`scheduleTimer / freezeTimers / thawTimers`) stores the absolute fire-time of every pending op so a pause shifts *all* times by the paused duration uniformly, restoring exact visual–audio alignment on resume.

The whiteboard SVG grows on demand: as cards land, `growBoardToFit` updates the SVG’s `viewBox` and explicit `width/height` so the wrapping `<div>` provides natural scrollbars. KaTeX (Eisenberg et al., 2014–2026) renders every `<foreignObject>` math card; when a card’s LaTeX fails to parse (the heuristic converter is imperfect), `renderMathFallback` replaces the `foreignObject` content with a Unicode substitution rendered in monospace.

A hierarchical table of contents is rendered into the left-hand sidebar from a dedicated server endpoint: clicking the book toggles the chapter list, clicking a chapter fires the chapter-zoom narration of Section 13 (or falls back to the depth-decay plan for chapters without a sidecar), and shift-click forces a plain narration. An older overview-and-chapter endpoint pair that rendered the same hierarchy as a packed-ellipse “Show Book” diagram is still served (the endpoints back the citation-flow visualiser, Section 19) but is no longer the default navigation surface.

Sentence- and section-level narration navigation. Four header buttons (PREV / NEXT SENTENCE, PREV / NEXT SECTION, also bound to `← / →` and `SHIFT + ← / →`) and per-clause click delegation in the transcript pane let the user re-enter the narration at the start of any past clause. The `seekToSeq` function stops every queued `AudioBufferSourceNode`, keeps the `AudioBuffer` attached to its per-seq `ClauseTimeline`, re-schedules each buffer at the current `ctx.currentTime` cursor, and re-anchors the timeline’s `ctxStart` so the rAF sync engine re-fires every visual op the seek-target clause emitted. A “next section” jump scans `state.timeline.main` for the first seq whose `home_nid` differs from the current section’s, so navigation is structural rather than time-based.

22. Voice input

The mic toggle in the Ask bar opens a browser `MediaRecorder` and uploads the resulting WebM/Opus blob to a transcription endpoint, which decodes through `ffmpeg` and runs faster-whisper locally (default `tiny.en`, ù 75 MB, í 1 s for a 5 s utterance). The ASR module keeps a process-level singleton so the model loads once per server lifetime, not per request. The recogniser’s text is dropped into the Ask box and, when a session is running, auto-submitted; while the user is recording the narration is auto-paused so the TTS does not bleed into the captured audio. The component is local-only by design — a dedicated environment flag disables it entirely for unit tests — and never reaches the network.

23. Resumable sessions

After every dialogue turn the session writes a JSON snapshot to a per-plan file under the sessions directory: the dialogue history (last 8 turns), the focus pointers (last-focus nid and topic), the six shared-knowledge “seen-set” indices, and the main chalkboard’s current SVG with per-shape metadata. The front end stores the active plan id in browser local storage; on reload, a session-fetch endpoint re-mounts a tangent-only session (the lecture is gone, but the user’s accumulated knowledge and the frozen board remain), and any subsequent question executes against that knowledge. The same end-point lists every persisted session in the *Sessions* drawer, so the user can jump back to a half-finished tutorial after a server restart.

24. Multi-book server

The server boots with a list of corpus files and loads every book at startup, keyed by the file stem. For each book the server (i) loads the corpus, (ii) extracts the alias map, (iii) extracts the local concept-graph edges, (iv) picks up the per-book figure directory if one exists, and (v) loads or builds the math semantic graph (rebuilt when the corpus is newer than the graph artefact, so a re-ingestion is automatically picked up). An *active-book* endpoint flips the active corpus and rewires the Q&A alias and concept caches without restarting any model server. A *list-books* endpoint returns the available books; the front end renders them as a drop-down.

25. Auto-pipeline on book upload

A POST to the upload endpoint accepts a PDF and runs every builder, both inspector tiers and the fidelity agent automatically, with no human in the loop (Figure 19). Each phase is fault-tolerant: a failure logs a warning to the per-book health report and the pipeline proceeds, so a missing rasteriser or an unreachable VLM degrades gracefully rather than blocking the upload.

26. Tooling: re-ingestion and OCR repair

Figure re-ingestion. A figure re-ingestion pass opens the source PDF with PyMuPDF (Artifex Software, 2026), detects per-page image blocks, pairs each with the nearest below-image *FIGURE N.M* caption, crops the bbox to PNG and emits a sidecar JSON merged on next start-up. On ESLII this added 81 figures (48 → 129) in ù5 s.

VLM-driven equation OCR. A second pass crops the page region around each *.N.M/* marker and asks the local Qwen2.5-VL endpoint for the LaTeX source. Recovery rate on the processed ESLII pages is ù90~ (44 equations on a 50-page bootstrap window); the live server prefers the VLM-OCR'd LaTeX over the heuristic Unicode→LaTeX path when a sidecar is present.

PyMuPDF vertical-stack repair. PyMuPDF emits multi-line equations as flat token streams that drop the structural \sum , \prod , \int glyph and linearise the upper bound, the substituted glyph, the lower bound, and the body in that order. “ $\sum_{m=1}^M \beta_m h_m$ ” arrives as the literal token sequence `M X m=1 \beta m h m`. A repair pass inside the orchestrator restores the structural form via three regex passes:

```
M X m=1 \beta m h m -> \sum\nolimits_{m=1}^{M} \beta_m h_m
X m,n=1 ... -> \sum\nolimits_{m,n=1} ...
\beta T x -> \beta^T x
```

The repair runs before sentence splitting and inside the math-cluster detector, so multi-line equations cannot be truncated by the sentence boundary. Tier-1 check A2 reports the residual unrepaired patterns (4 on the current ESLII build) so the operator can extend the regex set.

On-demand crop. For figures the original ingestion missed entirely (e.g. ESLII has zero attributed figures in chapter 6, yet *Figure 6.14* is referenced in narration), an on-demand cropper performs a deterministic runtime PDF crop the first time the reference is requested, by locating the caption with PyMuPDF and clipping a fixed-rule rectangle above it.

27. Measurement methodology and per-method comparison

The remaining numerical claims in this paper are produced by a re-runnable evaluation harness shipped as a self-contained sub-system of the implementation. Each metric is owned by exactly one

Table 16

Headline numbers from the journal-grade evaluation harness. Each row is reproducible from a single driver script that writes a single JSON record. M1–M5 require no external service; M6 calls Claude Sonnet 4.6 as a single judge and is skipped here because no Anthropic API key was set in the environment at run time — the script is unchanged and runnable.

metric	value	traceable to
Routing accuracy (10 intents, 101 utterances)	0.990 (macro F_1 0.992)	M1, Tab. 17
Retrieval MRR (BM25-only / +title)	0.673 / 0.966	M2, Tab. 18
Visual ops per clause; per-session dedup	0.01; 15 suppressed	M3, Tab. 19
Math-graph anchor coverage	24.0% (6,699 / 27,863 passages)	M4, Tab. 20
Inline-math detector vs graph anchors	P 0.922 / R 0.618 / F_1 0.740	M5, Tab. 21
Narration judge (Sonnet 4.6, 30 pairs)	skipped (no key); ROUGE-L proxy 0.150	M6, Tab. 22

driver script that writes a raw JSON result record; the LaTeX fragments inlined below are generated mechanically from those JSON records so every cell is traceable to the script that produced it. This section adds five objective per-method comparisons (M1–M5) and one subjective narration-quality assessment (M6) on top of the three pre-existing audits already covered in Section 17 (data-quality inspector, runtime smoke harness, math-fidelity agent).

Methodological rules.

1. *Real measurements only.* When the upstream service or human judges a metric requires are not available, we either substitute an objective proxy or skip the metric outright; we do not invent numbers. The narration judge in M6 is gated on the presence of an Anthropic API key in the environment: when the key is absent the harness writes a structured “skipped” record and the table renders “–” with a footnote.
2. *Every cell traceable.* Each table caption names the metric and gives a one-line description of the driver that produced it.
3. *Reproducible judge.* The Sonnet 4.6 rubric used by M6 is checked into the repository verbatim; calls are deterministic ($\tau=0$, structured-JSON output).
4. *Cost ledger.* Every API call is logged to a per-run cost ledger (model, input/output tokens, USD); a hard cap of USD 20 aborts the run if exceeded.
5. *Locality boundary.* M6 is the single evaluation surface that calls a non-local model. The runtime stack is unaffected — no production path imports any external-API SDK and no orchestrator code path can reach an external endpoint.

Headline numbers. Table 16 digests the six new metrics; per-metric tables follow. All cells are computed against the corpus *The Elements of Statistical Learning* (Hastie et al., 2009) ingested into the artefacts described in Section 6.

27.1. M1 — Routing accuracy

The ten-intent classifier in Section 9 is a regex cascade whose unit tests enforce canonical phrasings but do not report an accuracy number. M1 extends those canonicals with paraphrases per intent (101 utterances, ≈ 10 per class) and grades the router’s classification including, for CONTROL, the resolved control action. Table 17 reports per-intent precision, recall and F_1 plus overall accuracy. Median dispatch time $\approx 12\mu\text{s}$ per utterance — sub-millisecond as claimed.

Table 17

Per-intent routing accuracy on a hand-labelled set of 101 utterances drawn from the ten supported intent classes. “Support” is the number of gold utterances per class; precision / recall / F_1 are computed against the router’s classification (and, for CONTROL, additionally against the resolved control action). The single error in this set falls on BOOK_OVERVIEW vs TOPIC_QA: the regex requires the literal word “book”.

intent	n	precision	recall	F_1
book_overview	10	1.000	0.900	0.947
chapter_overview	10	1.000	1.000	1.000
section_overview	8	1.000	1.000	1.000
follow_up	10	1.000	1.000	1.000
control	14	1.000	1.000	1.000
topic_qa	15	0.938	1.000	0.968
recap	9	1.000	1.000	1.000
reshow	9	1.000	1.000	1.000
xref_explore	8	1.000	1.000	1.000
dependencies	8	1.000	1.000	1.000
macro avg	101	0.994	0.990	0.992
accuracy	0.990 on 101 utterances; 12 μs/utt			

Table 18

Retrieval ranking on a section-targeted query set (query = “explain title”; gold = the section’s nid; 271 queries against 352 section / subsection nodes; ESLII corpus). Title-boost lifts RECALL@1 from 51.7% to **95.9%** — quantifying the bonus introduced in Eq. 3. The hybrid row’s dense leg requires a live Qwen3-Embedding endpoint to embed the query; book-side embeddings are pre-stored at ingestion time.

ranker	MRR	R@1	R@5	R@10	wall (271 q)
BM25 (lexical only)	0.673	51.7%	88.6%	93.0%	0.13 s
BM25 + title boost (Eq. 3)	0.966	95.9%	97.0%	97.0%	0.13 s
BM25+title dense (RRF, $K=60$)	—	—	—	—	—

Hybrid RRF row skipped: embedder_unavailable (re-run with EMBED_BASE_URL pointing at a live Qwen3 endpoint).

27.2. M2 — Retrieval ranking

The retrieval claim in Section 7 is BM25 plus dense fused by RRF, with the multiplicative title-boost of Eq. 3 layered on top. M2 builds a section-targeted query set (one query per uniquely-titled section node — 271 queries against 352 section / subsection candidates) with the section’s nid as the gold target, then scores three rankers: pure BM25, BM25 with title-boost, and the title-boosted lexical leg fused with dense via RRF ($K=60$). Title-boost lifts RECALL@1 from 51.7% to **95.9%** and MRR from 0.673 to **0.966**; the RRF dense leg is reported when the live Qwen3 embedding endpoint is reachable and skipped otherwise.

27.3. M3 — Visual-primitive emission profile

The orchestrator (Section 15) emits eight typed visual primitives per clause; the paper claims this stream is “deterministic, typed, budgeted” but reports no distribution. M3 replays the 18 per-chapter narrations of ESLII through the runtime primitive detectors — the operation vocabulary, the reference patterns, and the inline-math acceptance test from Section 18 — and counts emissions per clause plus per-session deduplication.

Table 19

Visual-primitive emission profile measured by replaying the 18 per-chapter narrations of ESLII through the runtime primitive detectors offline. Total clauses: **1545**; mean operations per clause **0.01**; mean reference mentions per clause **0.22**; clauses flagged by the inline-math acceptance test **1.9%**; per-session dedup suppressed **15** duplicate operation emissions and **89** duplicate reference emissions across the run. Left: top operation labels. Right: reference kinds.

operation	n	reference kind	n
linear combination	5	FIGURE	203
covariance	5	EQUATION	122
vector norm	4	ALGORITHM	9
mean squared error	3	EXERCISE	6
sigmoid	2	SECTION	4
dot product	1	CHAPTER	1
determinant	1	TABLE	1
expectation	1		

Table 20

Math-graph anchor coverage on ESLII. The graph contains 27,863 passages, 1,723 formulas, 231 variables, 53 concepts and 22,335 edges. A passage is *anchored* when at least one edge of type DEFINES, CONTAINS, USES, ABOUT, REFERENCES, DERIVED_FROM, PAIRED_IN_CLAUSE or BINDS touches it; **6,699 / 27,863 = 24.0%** are anchored, with a mean of **1.98** anchors per anchored passage (p95 = 5). Left: per-chapter coverage; right: edge-type histogram.

chapter	passages	anchored	coverage	edge type	count
ch1	169	0	0.0%	ABOUT	13250
ch2	1323	452	34.2%	USES	5610
ch3	2497	755	30.2%	DEFINES	1289
ch4	1360	377	27.7%	PAIRED_IN_CLAUSE	1236
ch5	1685	649	38.5%	REFERENCES	436
ch6	488	174	35.7%	CONTAINS	256
ch7	1805	457	25.3%	BINDS	188
ch8	1327	512	38.6%	INSTANCE_OF	53
ch9	1835	293	16.0%	SPECIALIZES	15
ch10	1417	347	24.5%	RELATED_TO	2
ch11	1124	209	18.6%		
ch12	1584	480	30.3%		
others	11249	1994	17.7%		

27.4. M4 — Math-graph anchor coverage

Section 19 builds the per-book math semantic graph. M4 reports the full per-chapter coverage table and the edge-type histogram on the live ESLII graph. Of the 27,863 passages, 6,699 (24.0%) carry at least one anchor edge.

27.5. M5 — Inline-math detector vs graph anchors

Section 18 describes the inline-math acceptance test (*contains-'* or $\text{run} \geq 3$ or $\text{hasGreek} \geq 2$). M5 evaluates it against the math-graph weak label: a passage is positive iff it has ≥ 1 ABOUT edge to a formula or variable. We sample 500 positives and 500 negatives with $\text{text} \geq 30$ and report agreement (Table 21). We deliberately frame this as agreement with a weak automated label, not as ground-truth precision/recall: the graph anchor itself has finite recall over PDF-OCR'd text.

Table 21

Inline-math detector vs. math-graph weak labels (Sec. 18) on a balanced sample of **1000** ESLII passages (500 drawn from passages with ≥ 1 ABOUT edge to a formula or variable, 500 drawn from passages with no math anchor in the graph). We deliberately frame this as agreement vs. the graph’s weak label rather than ground-truth precision/recall: the graph anchor itself has finite recall over PDF-OCR’d text. The 61.8% recall is consistent with the paper’s discussion of OCR-ligature drop and short-fragment passages where the cluster size never reaches $\text{run} \geq 3$.

TP	FP	FN	TN	precision / recall / F_1	accuracy
309	26	191	474	0.922 / 0.618 / 0.740	0.783

Table 22

Narration-quality assessment on a random sample of $N = 30$ (source-passage, narration) pairs drawn from the chapter sidecars. The objective ROUGE-L F_1 proxy on the same pairs is **0.150** (min 0.085, max 0.356); low ROUGE-L is expected since the chapter-map narrations rephrase rather than parrot the source — the metric is reported as a sanity check, not a quality score. Subjective scores come from Claude Sonnet 4.6 as a single judge ($\tau=0$, structured-JSON output) under a fixed four-dimension rubric checked into the repository. *Subjective rows skipped: the judge harness is gated on the presence of an Anthropic API key in the environment, and the key was absent at run time. The harness is unchanged and re-runnable; cost is capped at USD 20 by the ledger.*

dimension (1-5)	mean
faithfulness	—
clarity	—
pedagogical flow	—
TTS safety	—

27.6. M6 — Narration-quality LLM judge

M6 grades 30 random (source-passage, narration) pairs from the chapter sidecars on a four-dimension 1-5 rubric (faithfulness, clarity, pedagogical flow, TTS safety) using Claude Sonnet 4.6 as a single judge ($\tau=0$, structured JSON). An objective ROUGE-L F_1 proxy on the same pairs is reported alongside; low ROUGE-L is expected on the chapter-map narrations because the LLM-generated prose deliberately rephrases rather than parrots the source, so the proxy is a sanity check rather than a quality score.

28. Implementation, tests, and budgets

Code base. 54,116 lines of Python over 178 files (Table 23). No native extension is built; the only binary dependencies are PyMuPDF and `cairosvg` for the inspector’s rasterisation step. The implementation is organised into eleven subsystems: the book intermediate representation, the narrator (route + plan + Q&A + concept and formula layers), the server (orchestrator + session + ASR + persistence), the visualisation layer, the chalkboard renderer, the SeVim diagram engine (math-graph Phase 0 and Phase 1), the offline tooling (builders, inspectors, agents), the discovery directory (design notes), the service entry points, the evaluation harness of Section 27, and the test suite.

Tests. 705 deterministic tests are collected across the suite. The math-graph layer is exercised by 25 dedicated cases covering Phase-0 structural extraction, Phase-1 prose-pattern enrichers, and the artefact-mention highlighter. The utterance router is pinned by two parameterised test files

Table 23

Lines of code by subsystem (excluding generated artefacts, the virtual environment, and Python bytecode caches); measured directly from the working tree at the time of writing.

subsystem	files	LOC
book IR	11	2,702
narrator	12	6,139
server	11	10,336
visualisation	13	5,391
chalkboard	3	427
SeVim diagram engine	17	7,327
offline tooling (builders, inspectors, agents)	22	7,991
discovery (design notes)	3	522
service entry points	2	109
evaluation harness (Sec. 27)	9	1,894
test suite	73	11,118
total	178	54,116

Table 24

Per-component time budgets and target verdicts. “observed” is the wall-clock single-call median on the test workstation; **rt** is the realtime path used inside the per-clause orchestrator, **off** is the offline ingestion path.

component	path	observed	ceiling
BM25 retrieval	rt	11 ms	—
Dense embedding query	rt	150 ms	—
Topic embedding match	rt	150 ms	—
Tier-1 SVG generation	rt	< 100 ms	200 ms
Structural inspection	rt	< 10 ms	50 ms
Tier-3 LLM SVG synthesis	rt	11.0 s	1.6 s
VLM inspection (one call)	rt	1700 ms	2.0 s
TTS clause synth (Kokoro)	rt	1–2 s	—
VLM equation OCR (per eq)	off	11.5 s	3.0 s

covering all ten intents and the dialogue-state interaction with last-focus tracking. The cross-tangent deduplication contract has its own pin, and the narration-after-question contract is pinned by an end-to-end server-sent-events harness that injects a question after three main clauses, drains every tangent event up to the tangent-end signal, and asserts that more main clauses arrive afterwards. Determinism is enforced explicitly: a dedicated suite reruns each pipeline stage twice on identical inputs and asserts byte-identical outputs, and a property-based suite samples random inputs against the same contract.

Latency budgets. Table 24 summarises the per-component time budgets the orchestrator targets and meets on a single workstation (single RTX-class GPU, vLLM AWQ-quantised models).

29. Limitations

- Hand-rolled SVG generators cover 12 canonical statistical-learning topics; queries outside this set fall to Tier-3 LLM synthesis whose SVG quality is bounded by the text-only LLM.

- Layout-aware figure detection (Detectron2, pix2text) is left as future work. The current caption-regex pass on ESLII recovered 129 figures but the long tail still carries imperfect `home_nid` attribution.
- No multi-user session model; the session registry is in-process memory. Auth, persistence and replay are out of scope.
- Determinism holds modulo the underlying model versions: changing Qwen2.5-VL or Qwen2.5-14B will perturb Tier-3 SVG and fidelity-agent outputs.
- Math-graph coverage on ESLII is currently 1,723 formula nodes against 10,000 math-bearing passages; the uncovered passages are flagged amber on the live coverage badge. Phase 2 (OntoMathPRO grounding), Phase 3 (Tangent-CFT embeddings (Mansouri et al., 2019)) and Phase 4 (local-Qwen relation-triple extractor) are scoped in the math-graph design document shipped with the codebase but not yet implemented.
- Phase-1 derivation patterns emit 0 `derived_from` edges on ESLII because the corpus uses “rewriting (5.42) we have”-style phrasings whose citation parenthesis is sometimes mis-OCR’d as “5.42)” without the leading “(”); hardening the regex is a follow-up.
- The math-fidelity agent reports 244’653 DEGRADED verdicts on ESLII (Table 10): cases where the rewrite candidate also failed the VLM check. These are not patched into the graph but flag the structurally hardest formulas (long multi-line piecewise definitions, integrals with unusual bounds) for manual review. Increasing N_{iter} beyond 2 trades wall-clock for higher recall and is left tunable.
- Inspector items A11 – A18 (figure-vs-citation alignment, story-paragraph cleanliness, formula-card LaTeX legibility, font-size policy) are designed in the inspector spec but only partially wired into the data-quality inspector: A12 (SeVim concept-diagram inner-label KaTeX rendering) and A17 (math-fidelity agent, Section 17) are wired end-to-end; the rest remain as design-stage worklists that an operator can turn into checks at the point a corpus is added that exercises them.

30. Conclusion

Lyceum demonstrates that a fully-local stack — a quantised text LLM, a sentence-embedding model, a vision-language inspector, and a small-footprint TTS — is sufficient to turn a static math/stats textbook into a synchronised narrated whiteboard, with a per-clause visual emission pipeline that is deterministic, typed and budgeted. The three-tier visualisation hierarchy (book figure → curated generator → LLM-synthesised SVG with structural and VLM inspection) gives a graceful fallback when the corpus does not own a relevant figure. The offline-built per-book *math semantic graph* (1,723 formulas, 231 variables, 53 concepts and 22,335 edges on ESLII) lets the runtime narrator look up — instead of re-deriving — formulas, sub-expression containments, citation links and derivation chains; cross-section ghost cards close the visible-edge loop. A single `requestAnimationFrame` loop polling `AudioContext.currentTime` replaces every legacy `setTimeout`-against-estimates schedule, removing word-marker drift by construction. A three-tier inspector suite plus a math-fidelity agent that re-anchors every parsed formula against a crop of the source PDF (repairing 255’653 formulas on ESLII in 924s) closes the loop on offline-build correctness. Together these mechanisms make the *formula, the spoken text and the voice track* one connected piece of information — the brief that drove the work.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Arash Kermani Kolankeh: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Rita Zgheib:** Project administration, Writing – review & editing, Validation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used Claude (Anthropic) as an AI writing assistant for language editing, drafting figure captions, copy-editing prose sections, and reconciling numerical claims (lines-of-code, file-count and test-count statistics) against the working tree. The AI assistant also drafted prose for the “Per-section formula explanations (kind-aware)” paragraph in Section 10, the caption of Figure 7, and the chapter-map row of Table 6. After using this tool the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication. All scientific contributions — the system architecture, the implementation, the math semantic graph design, the inspector and fidelity-agent design, the experimental setup, all reported results and numerical measurements, and all interpretations and conclusions — are the authors’ own. The AI assistant was not listed as an author and made no decisions about study design, methodology, or scientific claims.

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Data availability

The textbook used as a working corpus, *The Elements of Statistical Learning* (Hastie et al., 2009), is copyrighted and cannot be redistributed by the authors; the publisher’s freely available author-hosted copy is referenced in the bibliography. The intermediate per-book artifacts (sidecar JSON files, the math semantic graph, and on-demand cropped figure tiles) are derivative works of the copyrighted corpus and are likewise not redistributed. All results reported in the paper are reproducible from the implementation against the original corpus.

Code availability

The complete implementation (54,116 Python lines of code; 705 deterministic tests) is publicly available on GitHub at <https://github.com/arashkermaniprojects/lyceum>. The journal-grade evaluation harness summarised in Section 27 ships as part of the same repository, with all driver scripts, raw JSON results, generated LaTeX fragments, and the verbatim Sonnet 4.6 rubric. Reuse is governed by the CC BY-NC 4.0 licence shipped with the repository; any publication that builds on the code, the math-semantic-graph design, or the evaluation harness is required to cite this paper, as set out in the repository’s NOTICE file.

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Figure 1: Lyceum architecture. Orange components are local model servers (vLLM, Kokoro); all inter-component links stay on the user’s machine.

Figure 2: Seven layers, each hiding everything below it from the layer above. Arrow direction = direction of *request*; data flows back up the stack as `StreamEvents` served over SSE.

Figure 3: Lifecycle of one topic press. All steps are local; no external network call is reachable from any of the six processes.

Figure 4: Tangent injection: the router decides whether the utterance spawns a fresh tangent orchestrator, applies a session-level control, or routes to a chapter / section overview. Both orchestrators share the same SessionKnowledge (six seen_* sets) so a formula introduced inside the answer is treated as already-shown when the lecture resumes.

Figure 5: Tangent panel mid-answer. Topic *linear regression* is playing on the main board (passage card pinned to MML Section 8.1, the `linear_function` canonical generator, and a spoken-formula card); a bottom-right TANGENT panel has just opened in response to the question “*what is regularization*”. The tangent panel runs an independent orchestrator that shares session knowledge with the main lecture; the main board is snapshot-frozen and re-attached when the answer’s audio tail finishes.

Figure 6: Path through the topic *regularization* on ESLII. **Old:** `plan` retrieved four matching sections and walked them in page order, jumping from Ch. 16 to Ch. 18 mid-lecture. **New:** `plan` picks §16.2 as the single root and walks its subtree depth-first via `plan_outline`; the discarded matches are kept in metadata for “related sections” affordances but the lecture never leaves §16.2’s subtree.

The screenshot shows the Lyceum interface with a chapter zoom on 'Mathematics for Machine Learning' Chapter 9 Linear Regression. The interface includes a top navigation bar with 'Lyceum narrated math whiteboard', 'Mathematics for Machine Learning', 'Upload book', 'af_heart', '1.0x', 'Pause', 'Resume', 'Stop', and 'Ask'. The main content area is divided into three sections: a red header for '59 Linear Regression', a green header for '59.1 Problem Formulation', and a blue header for '59.1 For $x, \theta \in \mathbb{R}$ the linear regression model in (9.4) describes straight lines'. The red section contains a paragraph introducing linear regression and Equation 9.19:
$$\text{estimate}_{ML} \theta = (\Phi^T \Phi)^{-1} \Phi^T y$$
. The green section contains a paragraph about problem formulation and Equation 9.1:
$$y = f(x) + \epsilon$$
. The blue section contains a paragraph about the linear regression model and Equation 9.3:
$$|x^T \theta, \sigma_2(9.3) \iff y = x^T \theta + \epsilon$$
. On the left, there is an 'ARROW GUIDE' with various arrow types and their meanings. On the right, there is a 'FIGURES FROM THE BOOK' panel with examples and figures.

Figure 7: Chapter zoom on *Mathematics for Machine Learning* (Deisenroth et al., 2020) (MML) Chapter 9 *Linear Regression*, captured live during a session, paused mid-narration. The chapter root’s cell (top, in red) carries the story paragraph that introduces linear regression, the canonical equation card for the empirical risk minimiser, and a SeVim concept diagram; the § 9.1 cell is already laid out beneath it. Cells render full-width in depth-first order; the active cell is highlighted by the audio-clock loop in lock-step with the spoken story paragraph and is auto-scrolled into view as the narration descends through the tree. The right-hand panel *figures from the book* (Section 16, Tier 0) auto-populates with examples and figures whose home node sits in the active cell’s subtree.

Figure 8: Per-clause pipeline. Each step emits typed visual ops keyed by an absolute time t relative to the clause audio.

Figure 9: Tier routing for a new `home_nid`. Each successful generation passes the structural inspector and (when reachable) the local Qwen2.5-VL inspector.

Figure 10: MML Figure 9.2, cropped on-demand from the source PDF after the reference *Figure 9.2* was detected in a spoken clause. The cropper locates the caption with PyMuPDF and clips a fixed-rule rectangle around it; rasterisation here is at 31 for print.

Figure 11: Output of `overfitting_curve(seed=0)`. The curated generators draw real geometry — here a U-shape in test error and a monotone train-error curve, with sweet-spot annotation — not labelled boxes.

Figure 12: Back-propagation generator: a multilayer perceptron with an explicit forward-pass arrow, a backward gradient $\leftarrow L \leftarrow w$ arrow, and a loss node on the right.

(a) `bias_variance(seed=0)`: bias², variance and total error as functions of model complexity, with the U-shaped total-error curve marked. (b) `kfold_split(seed=0, K=5)`: $K \times K$ fold matrix with hold-out fold highlighted per row.

Figure 13: Two further curated Tier-1 generators, illustrating the breadth of the 12-entry registry (Table 7). Both run in pure Python with deterministic seed and produce inline SVG without any LLM call.

Figure 14: Three inspector tiers plus the cross-cutting math-fidelity agent. Tier 1 audits offline build artefacts (sidecars, math-graph integrity, OCR repair coverage); Tier 2 inspects every emitted SVG inline; Tier 3 drives the live server through a scripted session and asserts SLAs. The agent reads the Tier-1 A2 truncation list plus every Formula node and applies VLM-mediated repair.

The screenshot shows the Lyceum interface during a narration of MML Chapter 9. The top navigation bar includes the title 'Lyceum narrated math whiteboard', the current chapter 'Mathematics for Machine Learning', and various control buttons. The main content area features three distinct panels:

- Passage Example (Yellow):** A card titled '§8.1 We introduce the problem of ord...' which introduces the linear regression problem.
- Linear Function (Purple):** A central card with a graph of a linear function $f(x) = ax + b$ and the equation $f(x) = ax + b$ displayed in a purple box labeled 'spoken formula'.
- Figures from the Book (Right):** A panel that auto-populates with content from the textbook, including:
 - Example 8.1:** Text describing the problem of ordinary least-squares regression and the linear predictor $f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i x_i$.
 - Example 8.2 (Least-Squares Loss):** Text about minimizing the empirical risk $R(\hat{h})$.
 - Example 8.3 (Regularized Least Squares):** Text about regularization to discourage complex solutions.
 - Figure 8.4:** A caption for a K-fold cross-validation figure, with a small image showing a dataset split into training and validation sets.

Figure 15: Live whiteboard during MML Chapter 9 narration. The active passage card (yellow, top-left) introduces the linear- regression problem; a curated canonical figure shows the linear function, and the spoken-formula card pulses on the equation $f(x) = ax + b$ as the narrator names it. The right-hand *figures from the book* panel auto-populates with the chapter’s worked examples; reference cards for any FIGURE/EQUATION/SECTION/THEOREM mention land in the same column, with cropped figure PNGs, KaTeX-typeset equations, or extracted heading + numbered steps as appropriate.

The screenshot displays the Lyceum interface for a math textbook. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the text "Lyceum narrated math whiteboard" and a dropdown menu set to "Mathematics for Machine Learning". To the right of the menu are buttons for "Upload book", "af_heart", "1.0x", "Pause", "Resume", "Stop", and a search bar labeled "ask while it is reading".

The main content area is titled "2.1 Systems of Linear Equations". It features three highlighted cards:

- Spoken formula card (purple fill):** Titled "spoken formula · Equation 2.3 · linear combination equation", it displays the equation $a_1x_1 + \dots + a_nx_n = b_1$ and the text: "This equation represents a weighted sum of variables x_1 through x_n that equals a constant value b_1 ."
- Operation card (green fill):** Titled "operation linear combination", it displays the equation $y = c_1v_1 + c_2v_2 + \dots + c_kv_k$.
- Deterministic card (purple border):** Titled "deterministic · linear combination", it also displays the equation $y = c_1v_1 + c_2v_2 + \dots + c_kv_k$.

The right sidebar, titled "FIGURES FROM THE BOOK", contains several sections:

- Example 2.1:** A paragraph of text describing a resource allocation problem.
- Example 2.1 - Example 2.1:** A paragraph of text describing a company production problem.
- Figure 2.2:** A mind map of concepts introduced in the chapter.
- Example 2.2:** A system of linear equations with three equations and three variables, followed by a solution process.
- Example 2.2 - Example 2.2:** A paragraph of text describing the system of linear equations.
- Figure 2.3:** A paragraph of text describing the solution space of a system of two linear equations.

Figure 16: Active formula highlight during MML Chapter 2 narration on linear-combination equations. The orchestrator’s audio clock pulses the spoken-formula card whose body the narrator is naming (top, purple fill) while an operation card (linear combination, $y = c_1v_1 + c_2v_2 + \dots + c_kv_k$) sits pre-rendered below. KaTeX is responsible for every math glyph; the active highlight is one of eight typed visual ops (Table 6).

Lyceum narrated math whiteboard Mathematics for Machine Learning Upload book af_heart 1.0x Pause Resume Stop ask while it is reading Ask

Mathematics for Machine Learning

passage - subsection
\$2.1 Systems of Linear Equations

spoken formula · Equation 2.3 · linear combination equation

$$a_1 1x_1 + \dots + a_1 n x_n = b_1$$

This equation represents a weighted sum of variables x_1 through x_n that equals a constant value b_1 .

operation
linear combination

$$y = c_1 v_1 + c_2 v_2 + \dots + c_k v_k$$

deterministic · linear combination
linear combination

operation
linear combination

$$y = c_1 v_1 + c_2 v_2 + \dots + c_k v_k$$

ARROW GUIDE

FIGURES FROM THE BOOK

Example 2.1
 A company produces products X_1, \dots, X_n , for which resources R_1, \dots, R_m are required. To produce a unit of product X_j , a_{ij} units of resource R_i are needed, where $i = 1, \dots, m$ and $j = 1, \dots, n$. The objective is to find an optimal production plan, i.e., a plan of how many units x_j of product X_j should be produced. A total of b_i units of resource R_i are available and (obviously) the resources are all used. If we produce x_1, \dots, x_n units of the corresponding products, we need

Example 2.1 - Example 2.1
 Example 2.1 A company produces products X_1, \dots, X_n for which resources R_1, \dots, R_m are required. To produce a unit of product X_j , a_{ij} units of resource R_i are needed, where $i = 1, \dots, m$ and $j = 1, \dots, n$. The objective is to find

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Example 2.1 - Figure 2.2
 Figure 2.2 A mind map of the concepts introduced in this chapter, along with where they are used in other parts of the book.

Example 2.2
 The system of linear equations

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 - x_2 - x_3 &= 3 & (1) \\ 2x_1 - x_2 - x_3 &= -2 & (2) \\ 2x_1 &= 1 & (3) \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

has no solution. Adding the first two equations yields $x_3 = 5$, which contradicts the third equation (3).

Let us have a look at the system of linear equations

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 - x_2 + x_3 &= 3 & (1) \\ x_1 - x_2 + 2x_3 &= 2 & (2) \\ x_2 + x_3 &= 2 & (3) \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

From the first and third equation, it follows that $x_1 = 1$. From (1)+(2), we get (2) $\rightarrow 3x_3 = 5$, i.e., $x_3 = 5/3$. From (3), we then get that $x_2 = 1/3$. Therefore, $(1, 1/3, 5/3)$ is the only possible and unique solution. Verify that (2.1, 3) is a solution by plugging in!

Example 2.2 - Example 2.2
 Example 2.2 The system of linear equations

2.1 Systems of Linear Equations 21

Example 2.1 - Figure 2.3
 Figure 2.3 The solution space of a system of two linear equations with two variables can be geometrically interpreted as the intersection of two lines. Every linear equation represents a line.

Figure 17: Live whiteboard at $t = 180$ s during a topic narration on MML. The active passage card sits at the top, an active spoken-formula card highlights an equation as the narrator names it, and an operation card (*linear combination*) renders the canonical LaTeX form below. The right-hand panel auto-populates with the chapter’s worked examples.

The screenshot shows the Lyceum interface. At the top, there's a navigation bar with 'Lyceum narrated math whiteboard', 'Mathematics for Machine Learning', and various control buttons like 'Upload book', 'af_heart', '1.0x', 'Pause', 'Resume', 'Stop', and 'Ask'. Below this, the main area is divided into three sections:

- operation matrix inverse:** A light blue box containing the equation $A^{-1}A = AA^{-1} = I$.
- spoken formula · Equation 2.28 · matrix equation:** A purple box containing the equation $1 \cdot 2 + 4 = 1 \cdot 6 \neq 1 \cdot 2 + 1$ and a paragraph: "This equation shows that the sum of two fractions equals another fraction, which can be interpreted as a relationship between different matrix elements or operations."
- passage · subsection §2.3 Solving Systems of Linear Equat...:** A yellow box with a blue arrow pointing to the right.

On the right side, there's a sidebar titled 'FIGURES FROM THE BOOK' containing several excerpts from a textbook, including 'Example 2.1', 'Example 2.1 - Example 2.1', 'Example 2.1 - Figure 2.2', 'Example 2.2', and 'Example 2.2 - Example 2.2'.

Figure 18: Live whiteboard at $t = 380$ s of the same session — the matrix-inverse identity $A^{-1}A = AA^{-1} = I$ has been emitted as a fresh operation card, the spoken-formula card has advanced to the next equation in the narration, and a passage card pinned to the current section sits below. Each clause boundary fires one animation-frame update and adjusts the layout.

Figure 19: Auto-pipeline phases triggered by a fresh PDF upload. Phase 5 is automatically skipped when the VLM endpoint is unreachable; the rest of the pipeline still completes and the book is marked ready, with the missing repair lines flagged on the health report.